

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes with bis(pyridine)silver permanganate[†]

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Abstract : The oxidation of thirty-six *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes by bis(pyridine)silver permanganate (BPSP) resulted in the formation of the corresponding benzoic acids. The reaction is first order with respect to both BPSP and aldehydes. The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions. The rate of reaction increases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent. The correlation analyses of the rate of oxidation of thirty-six aldehydes were performed in terms of Charton's LDR and LDRS equations. The rate of oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes showed excellent correlation with Charton's LDR equation. The rates of *ortho*-compounds showed excellent correlation with LDRS equation. The oxidation *para*-compounds is more susceptible to the delocalization effect. The oxidation of *ortho*- and *meta*-compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. The polar reaction constants are negative indicating an electron-deficient centre in the rate-determining step. A mechanism involving a nucleophilic attack on the carbonyl group by a permanganate-oxygen and a subsequent hydride transfer has been proposed.

Keywords : Correlation analysis, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation, permanganate.

Introduction

Bis(pyridine)silver permanganate (BPSP) is mild and selective oxidizing agent. It is found to be better reagent than potassium permanganate in many reactions, e.g. oxidative alkylamination of electron-deficient (hetero) aromatic compounds¹. We have reported its thermally induced intra-molecular redox reaction² and the oxidation of oxalic and formic acid³ and of organic sulfides⁴ with BPSP. The oxidation of aldehydes with BPSP has not been reported, therefore, we have undertaken this work.

Results and discussion

The rate laws and other data were obtained for all compounds investigated. Since the results are similar only representative data are reproduced here.

The oxidation of aromatic aldehydes resulted in the formation of corresponding benzoic acid (1)

BPSP is reduced to Mn^{IV}. To confirm that Mn^{IV} is indeed formed as a result of reduction of BPSP by aldehydes, the rate were determined by monitoring the increase in [Mn^{IV}] at 418 nm also^{5,6}. The rates of decay at 529 nm and increase at 418 nm agreed within $\pm 7\%$. BPSP has virtually no absorption at 418 nm. This agrees with the observations of earlier workers^{5,6}.

Rate laws

The reactions are first order with respect to BPSP. Further, the values of k_{obs} , are independent of initial concentration of BPSP. The reaction rate increases linearly

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

with an increase in the concentration of aldehydes showing that the reaction is first order with respect to aldehydes also. The rate of oxidation increases linearly with an increase in the acidity of the solution (Table 1). Fig. 1 depicts a typical kinetic run.

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by BPSP at 298 K

10^3 [BPSP] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Aldehyde] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	1.0	2.33
1.0	0.20	1.0	4.62
1.0	0.40	1.0	9.36
1.0	0.60	1.0	14.0
1.0	0.80	1.0	18.2
1.0	1.00	1.0	23.3
1.0	2.00	1.0	46.7
2.0	0.40	1.0	9.36
4.0	0.40	1.0	9.56
6.0	0.40	1.0	9.12
8.0	0.40	1.0	9.61
1.0	1.00	0.2	4.70
1.0	1.00	0.4	9.32
1.0	1.00	0.6	14.1
1.0	1.00	0.8	18.7
1.0	0.40	1.0	9.54 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Fig. 1. Oxidation of benzaldehyde by BPSP : A typical kinetic run.

Test for free radicals : The oxidation of benzaldehyde, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. In blank experiments, with the aldehyde absent, no noticeable consumption of BPSP

was observed. The addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). To further confirm the absence of free radicals in the reaction pathway, the reaction was carried out in the presence of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of 2,6-di-*t*-butyl-4-methylphenol (butylated hydroxytoluene or BHT). It was found that BHT was recovered unchanged almost quantitatively.

Effect of solvent composition : The rate of oxidation was determined in solutions containing different amounts of acetic acid and water. It was observed that the rate of oxidation increased with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of solvent composition on the reaction rate

[BPSP]	[PhCHO]	[H ⁺]	$T = 298 \text{ K}$		
$1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	0.60 mol dm ⁻³	1.0 mol dm ⁻³			
% Acetic acid (v/v)	20	30	50	60	70
$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	5.76	10.5	14.0	24.6	38.0

Effect of substituents : The rates of oxidation of a number of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 3). The log k_2 at different temperature is linearly related to the inverse of the absolute temperature in all cases (Fig. 2). The Arrhenius equation is, therefore, valid for these oxidations.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the aldehydic C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of [²H]benzaldehyde (PhCDO) was studied. The results ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.66$ at 298 K) showed presence of a substantial primary kinetic effect (Table 3).

There is no satisfactory correlation between the activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the thirty-four aldehydes ($r^2 = 0.2736$), indicating the absence of a compensation effect⁷. A correlation between the calculated values of enthalpies and entropies is often vitiated by the experimental errors associated with them. The reaction, however, exhibited an excellent isokinetic relationship, as determined by Exner's method⁸. An Exner's plot between log k_2 at 288 K and at 318 K was linear ($r^2 = 0.9992$, slope = 0.8963 ± 0.0051) (Fig. 3). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the Exner's plot is $508 \pm 19 \text{ K}$. The linear isokinetic corre-

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by BPSP

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	8.80	23.3	57.6	139	67.3 ± 0.3	-70 ± 1	88.0 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -Me	18.5	47.0	113	252	63.8 ± 0.1	-76 ± 1	86.3 ± 0.1
<i>p</i> -OMe	43.0	105	234	556	62.0 ± 0.9	-75 ± 3	84.3 ± 0.7
<i>p</i> -F	10.6	28.8	72.0	176	68.2 ± 0.2	-64 ± 1	87.5 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -Cl	6.51	18.0	46.1	114	69.2 ± 0.3	-64 ± 1	89.2 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.52	1.71	4.90	14.0	79.6 ± 0.5	-56 ± 2	96.2 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -CF ₃	0.72	2.11	5.76	15.3	73.5 ± 0.2	-58 ± 1	92.3 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -COOMe	2.00	5.35	14.6	37.3	72.3 ± 0.3	-61 ± 1	91.0 ± 0.3
<i>p</i> -Br	6.32	17.5	44.6	112	68.4 ± 0.3	-64 ± 1	89.0 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -NHAc	22.0	52.5	127	290	63.0 ± 0.5	-75 ± 2	86.1 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -CN	0.90	2.81	8.00	21.4	78.0 ± 0.2	-53 ± 1	93.2 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -SMe	25.0	62.7	149	340	63.0 ± 0.2	-73 ± 2	86.5 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -NMe ₂	178	412	843	1770	50.5 ± 0.5	-81 ± 2	80.9 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -Me	17.7	40.0	97.0	220	64.3 ± 0.2	-70 ± 1	87.0 ± 0.2
<i>m</i> -OMe	16.5	41.5	98.3	224	63.8 ± 0.2	-81 ± 1	87.0 ± 0.1
<i>m</i> -Cl	2.70	7.41	19.9	46.3	68.9 ± 0.2	-70 ± 1	91.6 ± 0.2
<i>m</i> -Br	2.68	7.28	18.5	46.6	69.3 ± 0.4	-69 ± 2	91.5 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -F	3.35	0.07	23.4	54.1	66.8 ± 0.7	-75 ± 2	91.4 ± 0.3
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.30	0.91	2.53	7.05	77.1 ± 0.2	-58 ± 1	96.6 ± 0.2
<i>m</i> -CO ₂ Me	1.45	4.25	11.3	28.9	72.3 ± 0.2	-75 ± 1	92.8 ± 0.2
<i>m</i> -CF ₃	1.02	2.90	8.66	21.7	75.3 ± 0.8	-60 ± 3	93.7 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -CN	0.52	1.53	4.30	11.9	75.8 ± 0.6	-60 ± 2	95.7 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -SMe	11.4	29.0	66.6	145	62.5 ± 0.4	-79 ± 1	87.6 ± 0.3
<i>m</i> -NHAc	9.92	25.0	63.1	142	64.3 ± 0.3	-80 ± 2	87.7 ± 0.1
<i>o</i> -Me	80.0	182	400	812	55.3 ± 0.4	-87 ± 3	81.3 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -OMe	75.7	176	380	798	56.4 ± 0.2	-87 ± 2	83.2 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	1.00	2.74	7.41	19.8	73.5 ± 0.2	-60 ± 2	94.6 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -COOMe	6.60	17.2	41.0	98.7	65.2 ± 0.2	-79 ± 1	89.6 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -NHAc	112	252	520	1060	54.5 ± 0.2	-91 ± 2	82.4 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -Cl	19.2	46.7	107	233	60.6 ± 0.3	-85 ± 2	86.5 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -Br	25.4	61.6	137	308	59.9 ± 0.2	-82 ± 2	85.8 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -I	43.0	98.6	214	445	56.0 ± 0.2	-90 ± 2	84.8 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -CN	1.96	5.44	14.0	35.9	70.3 ± 0.2	-70 ± 3	92.0 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -SMe	108	240	490	1000	52.8 ± 0.3	-94 ± 2	82.6 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -F	43.0	30.8	72.5	170	63.4 ± 0.2	-80 ± 2	87.5 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -CF ₃	15.0	36.1	82.6	184	60.3 ± 0.1	-85 ± 2	82.3 ± 0.3
PhCDO	1.51	4.12	10.6	26.3	69.2 ± 0.4	-74 ± 2	92.4 ± 0.4
k_H/k_D	5.83	5.66	5.43	5.29			

lation implies that all the aldehydes are oxidized by the same mechanism and the change in the rate of oxidation is governed by changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of the activation.

Solvent composition effect

The rate of oxidation increases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in the solvent. This may be attributed to the change in the acidity of the medium with a

Fig. 2. Oxidation of benzaldehydes by BPSP : Effect of temperature.

Fig. 3. Exner's isokinetic relationship in the oxidation of benzaldehydes by BPSP.

change in the amount of acetic acid. Hammett's acidity function, H_0 , for low concentration of perchloric acid in a series of acetic acid-water mixtures has been determined⁹. It is observed that the acidity increases as the concentration of acetic acid increases. The present reaction is an acid-catalyzed one and with an increase in the acidity of the solution, the rate is expected to increase.

Correlation analysis of reactivity

The rate constants for the oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes were correlated in terms of Hammett equation¹⁰ but no significant correlation was obtained [eq. (2)].

$$\log k_2 = -2.04 \pm 0.21\sigma - 2.87 \quad (2)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8973, sd = 0.31, n = 24, T = 298 \text{ K}$$

It has been stated^{10a} that in the absence of proximity effects, the polar effects of *ortho*-substituents parallel those of *para*-substituents. In this case, however, the rate constants of *ortho*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes are not linearly related [eq. (3)]. This indicates that the polar effects are not solely responsible for the observed effect of *ortho*-substituents on this reaction.

$$\log k_{ortho} = 1.21 \pm 0.22 \log_{para} - 2.94 \quad (3)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9034, sd = 0.27, n = 11, T = 298 \text{ K}$$

There have been many attempts to describe a single substituent-parameter equation for *ortho*-substituents. Charton^{10a} has compiled a list 32 sets of such constant. We analyzed the rate constants of the *ortho*-compounds in terms of *ortho*-substituent constant, σ_o , of Tribble and Traynham^{10b} which has the biggest set of data, but the correlation is unsatisfactory [eq. (4)].

$$\log k_2 = -1.01 \pm 0.25 \sigma_o - 3.07 \quad (4)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6235, sd = 0.46, n = 11, T = 298 \text{ K}$$

The data for *o*-NO₂ and *o*-SMe were not included in this correlation as the σ_o values are not available.

Since the rate constants failed to yield satisfactory correlation with any single substituent-parameter equation, the rates were analyzed in terms of Taft's¹¹ and Swain-Lupton's¹² dual substituent-parameter equations. However, no satisfactory correlation was obtained in these equations also. In the late 1980s, Charton¹³ introduced a triparametric LDR equation for the quantitative description of structural effects on chemical reactivities. In this work we have applied the LDR equation [eq. (5)] to the rate constants, k_2 .

$$\log k_2 = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + h \quad (5)$$

Here, σ_1 is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized electrical effect parameter when the active site electronic demand is minimal and σ_e represents the sensitivity of the substituent to changes in electronic demand by the active site. The latter two substituent parameters are related by eq. (6).

$$\sigma_D = \eta\sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (6)$$

Here η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site and is given by $\eta = R/D$, and σ_D represents the

delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric LD equation.

For *ortho*-substituted compounds, it is necessary to account for the possibility of steric effects and Charton¹³, therefore, modified the LDR equation to generate the LDRS eq. (7).

$$\log k_2 = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + Sv + h \quad (7)$$

where v is the well known Charton's steric parameter based on Van der Waals radii¹⁴.

The rates of oxidation of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes show an excellent correlation in terms of the LDR/LDRS equations (Table 4). We have used the standard deviation (*sd*), the coefficient of multiple determination (R^2), and Exner's parameter¹⁵, ψ , as the measures of goodness of fit.

The comparison of the L and D values for the substituted benzaldehydes showed that the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzaldehydes is more susceptible to the delocalization effect than to the localized effect. However, the oxidation of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. In all cases, the magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature, pointing to a decrease in selectivity with an increase in temperature.

All three regression coefficients, L, D and R, are negative indicating an electron-deficient carbon centre in the activated complex for the rate-determining step. The positive value of η adds a negative increment to σ_d , increas-

ing the electron-donating power of the substituent and its capacity to stabilize a cationic species. The positive value of S indicates that the reaction is subject to steric acceleration by an *ortho*-substituent.

To test the significance of localized, delocalized and steric effects in the *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes, multiple regression analyses were carried out with (i) σ_1 , σ_d and σ_e , (ii) σ_d , σ_e and v and (iii) σ_1 , σ_e and v . The absence of significant correlations showed that all the four substituent constants are significant.

$$\log k_2 = -1.48 (\pm 0.43) \sigma_1 - 1.69 (\pm 0.34) \sigma_d - 3.53 (\pm 1.94) \sigma_e - 2.53 \quad (8)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8273; sd = 0.54; n = 12; \psi = 0.47$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.78 (\pm 0.44) \sigma_d - 1.82 (\pm 2.73) \sigma_e + 0.89 (\pm 0.50) v - 3.46 \quad (9)$$

$$R^2 = 0.7031; sd = 0.63; n = 12; \psi = 0.63$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.96 (\pm 0.69) \sigma_1 - 0.43 (\pm 3.31) \sigma_e + 1.31 (\pm 0.62) v - 2.62 \quad (10)$$

$$R^2 = 0.5644; sd = 0.47; n = 12; \psi = 0.47$$

Similarly in the cases of the oxidation of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzaldehydes, multiple regression analyses indicated that both localization and delocalization effects are significant. There is no significant colinearity between the various substituents constants for the three series.

The percent contribution¹³ of the delocalized effect, P_D , is given by following eq. (11).

$$P_D = (|D| \times 100) / (|L| + |D|) \quad (11)$$

Table 4. Temperature dependence for the reaction constants for the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by BPSP

T (K)	L	D	R	S	η	R^2	<i>sd</i>	ψ	P_D	P_S
<i>para</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.48	-1.98	-1.24	-	0.76	0.9996	0.008	0.03	57.2	-
298	-1.39	-1.84	-1.16	-	0.76	0.9999	0.004	0.01	57.0	-
308	-1.30	-1.73	-1.07	-	0.75	0.9994	0.011	0.04	57.1	-
318	-1.21	-1.65	-1.00	-	0.73	0.9989	0.015	0.07	57.7	-
<i>meta</i> -Substituted										
288	-2.07	-1.50	-1.21	-	0.81	0.9978	0.013	0.06	42.0	-
298	-1.96	-1.41	-1.14	-	0.81	0.9999	0.005	0.01	41.8	-
308	-1.86	-1.33	-0.97	-	0.74	0.9991	0.011	0.04	44.2	-
318	-1.77	-1.25	-0.92	-	0.74	0.9994	0.008	0.03	41.4	-
<i>ortho</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.85	-1.74	-1.32	1.38	0.76	0.9993	0.012	0.05	48.4	27.8
298	-1.76	-1.66	-1.29	1.27	0.78	0.9998	0.007	0.02	48.5	27.1
308	-1.66	-1.55	-1.15	1.18	0.74	0.9999	0.006	0.01	48.3	26.9
318	-1.55	-1.45	-1.04	1.10	0.72	0.9985	0.021	0.08	48.3	26.8

Scheme 2

10^{-2} . Benzaldehyde, therefore, hydrated to an extent of *ca.* 1% in solution. In view of this, the involvement of the hydrated form is less likely.

Experimental

BPSP was prepared by reported method²⁰ and its purity was checked by iodometric method. The aldehydes were commercial products. The liquid aldehydes were purified through their bisulfite addition compounds and distilling them, under nitrogen, just before use²¹. The solid aldehydes were recrystallized from ethanol. Deuteriated benzaldehyde (PhCDO) was also prepared by the literature method²². Its isotopic purity, as ascertained by its NMR spectrum, was $97 \pm 5\%$. Perchloric acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Acetic acid was refluxed with acetic anhydride and chromic oxide for 2 h and then distilled.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, freshly distilled benzaldehyde (0.05 mol) and BPSP (0.01 mol) were made up to 50 cm³ in 1 : 1 acetic acid-water (v/v) and kept in the dark for *ca.* 10 h to ensure completion of the reaction. It was rendered alkaline with NaOH, filtered and filtrate evaporated to under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in minimum amount of conc. HCl and cooled in ice to yield crude acid (2 g), which was recrystallized from hot water to produce pure benzoic acid (1.9 g, 90%, m.p. 121 °C).

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were studied under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large

excess of the aldehyde ($\times 15$ or larger) over BPSP. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water, unless stated otherwise. The reactions were studied at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and followed up to 80% completion by monitoring the decrease in absorption due to BPSP at 529 nm. The pseudo-first order constants, k_{obs} , were computed from the linear ($r > 0.990$) least-squares plots of $\log [\text{BPSP}]$ versus time plots. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that rate constants are reproducible within $\pm 4\%$. Preliminary experiments showed that the oxidation is not sensitive to changes in ionic strength; therefore, no attempt was kept it constant.

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